

DAMAGE PROCESS MODELING ON SMC

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ABSTRACT

Damage process taking place in SMC subjected to the monotonically increasing tensile load is analysed and the stress-strain curve is calculated. SMC is viewed as a laminate consisting of fibre bundles embedded in the resin/filler matrix. The stiffness of bundles and matrix are expected to be reduced through the developing cracks which lead to the reduction of the total stiffness of SMC. Crack creation and consequent bundle and matrix stiffness reduction are viewed as a statistic process. The quadratic criterion in stress space and the maximum strain criterion are used to predict a failure in the fibre bundles and in the matrix, respectively. Residual stresses resulting from the high curing temperature as well as anisotropic fibre orientation and varying content of filler particles in the matrix inside and outside of bundles are taken into account. The comparison of predicted stress-strain curves to the experimental results obtained on almost 20 different SMC materials shows a very good agreement especially at elongations lower than 1%. The model allows for the appreciation of the quantitative influence of different materials and processing parameters on SMC behaviour and, in this way, to optimize its composition.

INTRODUCTION

A typical feature of the SMC structure is that the glass roving does not disintegrate into individual fibres in the cutter. Instead, flat fibreglass bundles, oriented parallel to the direction of the take-up belt, are formed and behave as effective reinforcing agents. The tightly packed fibres in the bundles act like a sieve, preventing larger filler particles from penetrating into the internal bundle space. The particle distribution in the matrix, therefore, can be considerably non-homogeneous. SMC can be viewed as an aggregate of micro-laminae stacked one upon the other and, under in plane loading, the uniform strain concept and from it the laminate analogy can be applied [1]. The properties of SMC's are determined by the composition of the material and by the properties of their constituents as well as by the process parameters. Significant residual stresses take place in the SMC structure with cool down from processing temperature. Cooling generates local transverse tensile stresses in fibre bundles and in the matrix, which results in considerable local reduction in the load bearing capacity and can significantly contribute to the initiation of micro-cracking at ambient conditions.

The influence of individual structural, material and processing parameters on the degradation of the SMC properties under monotonically increasing tensile load is examined in this paper.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL

SMC is viewed as a multilayer composite material consisting of identical layers. It is assumed that the individual layers are void-free and adhere firmly to one another. For volume fractions, v , of individual components, resin compound (r), filler (p) and fibre (f), the following applies: $v_r + v_p + v_f = 1$

A. Initial Thermo-Elastic Properties

The fundamental element of the SMC structure is the fibre bundle saturated by the matrix (resin/filler mixture, which is assumed as isotropic with elastic properties E_{mi} , ν_{mi} , α_{mi}). It represents an UD-composite, the thermo-elastic parameters (TEP) of which (moduli E_L , E_T , G_{LT} , G_{TT} , Poisson's ratios ν_{LT} , ν_{TT} and thermal expansion coefficients (TEC) α_L , α_T) can be calculated in terms of the TEP of fibres and matrix, e.g., using the formulae by Hashin [2]. It was determined from polished sections of SMC specimens that the fibre glass fraction, Φ_f , in the fibre bundle is about 50% by vol. The TEP of matrix can be calculated by combining the formulae of Kerner and Hashin [1] or using the "S-combining-Rule" [4], when isotropic and roughly spherical filler (e.g. calcium hydrate) is used. If the filler particles are uniformly distributed in the whole volume of SMC, the filler fraction Φ_{pi} in the matrix (resin/filler mixture) is $\Phi_{pi} = v_p / (v_r + v_p)$. Due to a "sieve effect" of fibre bundles, the filler fraction in the internal space, Φ_{pe} , can be smaller than that in the matrix surrounding the bundles (Φ_{pe}). That is $0 \leq \Phi_{pe} \leq \Phi_{pi}$.

Figure 1. Representation of SMC by means of a multilayer composite consisting of UD-plyies. Designation of the coordination system.

Between Φ_{pi} and Φ_{pe} the following relation exists:

$$\Phi_{pe} = \frac{v_p - \Phi_{pi} v_f}{v_p + v_r - v_f} \quad (1)$$

On the basis of the TEP's of resin compound and filler and of the filler fractions Φ_{pi} and Φ_{pe} , the TEP's of "internal" as well as of "external" matrices- E_{mi} , ν_{mi} , α_{mi} , E_{me} , ν_{me} , α_{me} , can be calculated.

The fibre bundles saturated by the "internal" matrix are the effective reinforcing elements and can be viewed as "macroscopic" fibres with anisotropic properties embedded in the "external" matrix. Bundle volume fraction in SMC is then $\Phi_B = 2v_f$. The bundles are randomly distributed in the SMC and differently oriented with respect to the certain coordination system O_1, O_2 (Figure 1). Collecting all the bundles lying in the same direction into one ply, the stochastic structure is transformed in the multilayer composition, consisting of UD-plyies having identical TEP's. The stiffness matrix of the total laminate is then determined by summing up the stiffnesses of individual layers in the direction of elected coordinate axes O_1, O_2 . These stiffnesses are obtained using the well-known transformation formulae (e.g. [5]) as functions of the orientation angle ω . In the case, when the bundle distribution is non-uniform with respect to the orientation angle ω and is described by a distribution function $H(\omega)$, the elements of the laminate initial stiffness matrix can be obtained by:

$$\overline{C_{ij\sigma}} = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} H(\omega) C_{ij\sigma}(\omega) d\omega \quad (2)$$

With respect to the results of Starke and Michaeli [9] the distribution function $H(\omega)$ was accepted in the following form:

$$H(\omega) = C + A \cdot e^{-B\omega^2} \quad (3)$$

where A, B and C are constants.

The function $H(\omega)$ is symmetric about the O_1 -axis (where $\omega=0$). The case $B=0$ relates to the uniform distribution of bundles. In this case, the SMC is planar isotropic. The material properties become orthotropic with the extreme values at $\omega=0^\circ$ and $\omega=90^\circ$ when $B>0$.

The integration shown in equation (2) is only possible numerically. When the stiffness matrix elements are determined, then initial planar TEP's of SMC in the direction of its orthotropic axes O_1, O_2 , can be calculated.

B. Residual stresses

Due to a mismatch in thermo-elastic properties of the laminate constituents (fibre bundles, resin compound and filler), thermal stresses arise in the laminate structure while cooling down from the elevated processing temperature. These stresses are sufficiently large enough in SMC to influence the damage process and thus cannot be neglected.

The SMC is modelled as an aggregate of UD-plyies, therefore, the state of stresses in these plyies has to be analysed. Every ply is considered to be firmly connected within the entire SMC material and thus possesses identical deformations while SMC dilates. In the case of non-uniform bundle distribution (parameter $B>0$) these thermal stresses are also functions of the ply orientation angle ω .

Along with the creation of the residual stresses in the fibre bundles, residual stresses also take place in the bundle surrounding matrix (resin/filler mixture). It is assumed that the matrix deformation is planar and identical to the deformation of the laminate.

Because of the strong temperature dependency of all TEPs, the residual stresses depend not only on the magnitude of temperature difference ΔT , but also on the courses of TEPs within the temperature interval. It can be assumed that TEPs of fibres and filler are constant up to a temperature of 200°C. The accepted temperature functions of the resin properties used in the theoretical considerations are shown in Figure 2.

The calculations of residual stresses are realized in small steps of ΔT , within which the constant values of entering elastic parameters can be accepted. The final values of the stresses are obtained as a sum of individual stress increments. The graphical presentation of the plots of residual stresses as function of the structural parameter Φ_{pi} can be found in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Temperature functions of the resin properties

Figure 3. Development of the residual stress σ_{RT}

C. Cracking mechanism

SMC is assumed to be found under the condition of monotonically increasing tensile load, acting in the direction of the axis O_1 , and having all plies at the beginning of the load intact. The strength of a ply is a function of its orientation angle. The strength of a unidirectional laminate depends on the loading direction and possesses the extreme values in the direction of axes O_L , O_T . The state of stressing is planar and has three components: σ_L , σ_T , σ_{LT} . The stress σ_L is known to have no effect on a crack along the fibres (within the matrix or along the fibre-matrix interface). The creation of these cracks thus depends on σ_T and σ_{LT} only. The elliptic failure criterion is accepted in the following form:

$$\frac{\sigma_T^2}{R_T^2} + \frac{\sigma_{LT}^2}{R_{LT}^2} = 1 \tag{4}$$

where R_T and R_{LT} are tensile and shear strengths, which have to be determined experimentally. In a multilayer composite, however, the local fracture propagates through the layer and causes a stress concentration in the adjacent, but unfractured laminae, which arrests its further propagation. The damaged ply cannot support any transverse tensile or shear load in the vicinity of the crack and its contribution to the total stiffness is in this way reduced. Its stiffness in the fibre longitudinal direction remains unaffected. Several studies have been carried out to experimentally as well as theoretically establish the quantitative influence on laminate properties resulting from the initiation and growth of cracks.

It yields from the gaussian character of the strength quantities R_T and R_{LT} , that the most frequent crack initiation takes place at stresses of values near R_T and R_{LT} , which correlates with the maximum rate of stiffness reduction, found by Highsmith and Reifsnider [7]. A similar behavior

can be deduced also from the experiments carried out by Tsai and Hahn [6] on the cross-ply laminates, when a crack appearance doesn't lead to the failure, as the crack effect is constrained (and through it localized) by adjoining plies. Their results show that the effective stiffness reduction of the cross oriented layer amounts to about 40 %, when the stress $\sigma_T = R_T$ is reached in this layer. The degradation function D_b , describing the stiffness reduction of bundles, was therefore accepted in the form:

$$D_b(\sigma_T, \sigma_{LT}) = 1 - e^{-(0,707 \frac{\sigma}{R})^2} \quad (5)$$

Figure 4 demonstrates the acceptance made for σ and R for biaxial state of stressing.

Figure 4.

A similar procedure is also used when calculating the effect of crack creation on the effective stiffness of matrix surrounding bundles. The maximum strain criterion is used in this case. The degradation function, describing the stiffness reduction of the external matrix is thus defined by equation (5), when substituting σ and R_T for corresponding elongations. The ultimate elongation ϵ_{mu} depends on the filler fraction Φ_{pe} and on the properties of resin, especially on its toughness. Based on the experimental results carried out on mixtures of calcium carbonate filler and UP-resins possessing different tensile elongations ϵ_{ru} , the dependence of ϵ_{mu} on ϵ_{ru} and Φ_{pe} was found in the following form:

$$\epsilon_{mu} = 1,5 \sqrt{\epsilon_{ru}} (1 - 1,04 \sqrt[3]{\Phi_{pe}}) \quad (6)$$

In this way, the stiffness of every layer can be defined according to its level of stressing and the total laminate stiffness is found as a sum of stiffnesses of degraded layers. The moduli of elasticity of SMC are calculated at stepwise increasing strain ϵ_1 and the corresponding stress σ_1 is then determined for every individual value of ϵ_1 assuming the SMC response to be linear. By this procedure, the σ - ϵ curve is obtained describing the behaviour of SMC when damage process takes place.

COMPARISON OF MODEL PREDICTIONS TO EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The accuracy of model predictions depends substantially on the correctness of data used in the calculations. There are the values of the strength quantities R_T and R_{LT} , which are of considerable importance when modelling the damage process on SMC. Unfortunately, very little data were found in the literature concerning the glass fibre/UP composites. The R_T values were found to lie within the interval from 12 to 32 MPa, while R_{LT} values were determined to lie between 40 and 55 MPa. The measurements were carried out on specimens with fibre fractions greater than 60% by vol. prepared by filament winding. In the case of SMC, however, the mean fibre fraction in bundles is about 50%. For this as well as other reasons, the application of the above mentioned strength values is connected with a considerable amount of uncertainty.

Tensile tests were thus carried out on specimens prepared of UP resin reinforced by glass mat and cured at the temperature of 22°C in order to prevent the existence of thermal residual stresses. A very good approximation was obtained using the values $R_T = 30$ MPa and $R_{LT} = 50$

MPa. These strength values were thus applied in all further predictions.

The experimental results obtained by Altstädt [8] were used to test the possible accuracy of predictions. Altstädt examined the behavior of nearly 30 types of R-SMC materials prepared of different combinations of resin (3 types), glass fibre reinforcements (4 types), filler (4 types) and shrinkage compensators (2 types). All the necessary data concerning the properties of constituent materials of composites and processing conditions were forthcoming in nearly all cases, which made the results convenient for prediction purposes.

The measurements were always carried out using a set of 6 specimens, the basis for which the mean stress-strain curves were determined. The dispersion of the stress-strain plots was found to be large, especially in the region of higher strains.

Results of the investigation of the influence of the filler ratio are presented in Figure 5. The prediction results were calculated holding the fibre volume fraction of $v_f=0,22$ constant. It can be seen, that increasing the filler content causes an increase in SMC stiffness and the material also obtains a greater tendency to form a "knee".

Figure 6 presents the results of investigations for the resin toughness effect along with the predicted curves. Both the experimental and theoretical plots of stress-strain curves show the deformation behavior of SMC to be clearly influenced by resin toughness, especially at the beginning of loading. Decreased resin toughness consequently leads to lower stress levels within which the linear stress-strain dependence is acceptable. The tendency to form a "knee" also becomes more obvious.

The influence of the filler particle size distribution can be modelled, assuming that the larger particles cannot penetrate into the bundles. This means that the fibres are connected by a pure resin in this extreme case. In the other extreme case the filler particles are homogeneously distributed in the SMC. The plots corresponding to these boundary cases can be found in Figure 7. The theoretical results show, that if the filler particles are large enough not to be able to penetrate into the bundles, then it can be expected that a more distinct "knee" is formed.

Figure 5. Effect of filler ratio on the stress-strain behavior of SMC (predicted curves for $v_f = 0,22 = \text{const}$)

Figure 6. Experimental and predicted stress-strain SMC plots when resins of different ultimate tensile elongation are applied.

Figure 7. Influence of filler particle size distribution on SMC stress-strain plots.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The comparison of predictions to the experimental results shows that the developed model is able to describe the behavior of SMC under tensile loading very well, especially at the beginning of the loading phase. When a higher level of crack density is reached, the damage process

gradually becomes of a local character, which the model is not able to take into account. Substantial differences between experimental and theoretical curves in the second half of the loading cycle can be caused also by the initial anisotropy of the investigated SMC samples. To prevent the misrepresentation of results due to material anisotropy, measurements on specimens cut in two mutually perpendicular directions are always necessary.

The model includes the influence of many materials as well as processing parameters, which permits the evaluation quantitatively of the influence of individual parameters and, in this way, to optimize the SMC properties. The following general conclusions can be reached:

- the behaviour of SMC is substantially influenced by the distribution of the filler particles. Optimal SMC behaviour can be expected when enough fine particles are applied and a homogeneous filler distribution is reached throughout the entire SMC volume.
- the residual stresses (σ_{RT}) acting transversal to the fibre direction and in the matrix are tensile in character and can reach a level that is comparable to the strength values. Reducing the residual stresses seems to be a very promising way to improve the application limits of SMC.
- the crack resistance is governed by the resin properties, especially by their toughness and adhesion ability. The final tensile stiffness of SMC is governed by the fibre content and, therefore, a small loss in stiffness - when a more ductile and eventually of lower elasticity modulus resin is applied - can be balanced through slightly enhancing the fibre fraction.
- the creation of cracks is directionally dependent. The stiffness loss rate is higher in the loading direction than in the transversal one. Consequently, SMC behaviour becomes anisotropic in nature, and in addition this level of anisotropy is changed if the SMC material is initially anisotropic in nature.

The model is based on the assumption that SMC as well as all its constituents behave linearly elastic. In spite of this simplification and incomplete knowledge of much of the necessary data, encouraging results were obtained. Thus, it appears that further investigation in this area will provide a powerful and useful tool in understanding the complexity of SMC materials and their applications.

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